

Inside the criminology of Carlo Morselli

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February 2022

This is the pre-publication version of this article. The final version appeared here:

Bouchard, M., Ouellet, F. (2022). Inside the criminology of Carlo Morselli. *Canadian Journal of Criminology and Criminal Justice*, 64: 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.3138/cjccj.2022-0010>

ABSTRACT

Dr. Carlo Morselli's research inspired numerous scholars around the world to integrate criminal achievement indicators and social network data into their research program. As a Professor of Criminology for over 20 years at Université de Montréal, Carlo's contributions was part of a generation of scholars who act as brokers between Canada's two official languages. This volume of the *Canadian Journal of Criminology and Criminal Justice* brings together research inspired by his legacy. Carlo's interests were diverse; we selected manuscripts revolving around two major themes in Carlo's career: the development of criminal achievement as a conceptual and empirical framework, and the innovative use of social network data in new contexts of criminological interest, such as the role of social networks in individuals' relative optimism towards desistance, or in future victimization.

Keywords: Illicit networks; Organized Crime; Criminal achievement; Social Network Analysis; Carlo Morselli.

RÉSUMÉ

Les recherches du professeur Carlo Morselli ont amené de nombreux chercheurs à travers le monde à tenir compte de la réussite criminelle et des réseaux sociaux dans leurs propres travaux. Dans son rôle de professeur en criminologie à l'université de Montréal, Carlo a agi en tant que courtier entre les deux langues officielles canadiennes. Ce numéro de la Revue canadienne de criminologie et de justice pénale rassemble des recherches empiriques inspirées par son travail. Les intérêts de Carlo étaient variés; Les articles présentés portent sur deux grands thèmes ayant marqué la carrière de Carlo : le développement du cadre conceptuel et empirique entourant la réussite criminelle, et l'utilisation dans de nouveaux contextes d'intérêt en criminologie de données issues des réseaux sociaux pour mieux comprendre certains enjeux, notamment le rôle que peut jouer les réseaux d'une personne dans son attitude envers le désistement ou encore dans sa victimisation future.

Mots clés : Réseaux criminels ; Crime organisé; Réussite criminelle ; Analyse des réseaux sociaux ; Carlo Morselli.

The passing of Dr. Carlo Morselli in October 2020 was many decades too soon, hitting all of us who knew him or his work very hard. Carlo had been battling cancer for a few years, beating the initial prognostics he received when the cancer was discovered. A few months after his diagnosis, Carlo started to take a deep interest in experimental cancer treatments that use neural network analysis to target the broker cells responsible for spreading cancer. We don't know exactly how far his quest went, but we know he was hoping to establish collaborative ties with cancer researchers so that both subfields of network scholarship could learn from the discoveries made in the other. A collaborative, innovative network scholar through and through until the very end.

INSERT PHOTO 1 OF CARLO MORSELLI ABOUT HERE

Carlo obtained his PhD from the School of Criminology at Université de Montréal in 2001 where he was soon hired as a member of the faculty. In this position, he played a crucial role in the development of Canadian Criminology for over 20 years, including in his role as a former Director and researcher at the International Centre for Comparative Criminology and long-time editorial board member of the *Canadian Journal of Criminology and Criminal Justice*. As one of our mentors (i.e. the authors), Carlo was there to make things light when we needed it most. Taking things too seriously? Taking yourself too seriously? He would listen, he would shake his head, tilt it to the side, and start smiling... and it was all we needed. Carlo encouraged all of us to find our own academic identity. To stay true to who we were. His mentorship was not dogmatic; it was personalized. It encouraged reading broadly, it encouraged creativity, it encouraged us to find purpose. To make our writing clearer and more alive, for instance, he often told us to write with someone in mind, someone that needs to be convinced, someone who would disagree:

Don't write with your friends in mind, they already agree. Write with an enemy in mind, someone who would challenge your ideas.

His own scholarship was creative, innovative, and inspiring. His love for biographies of criminals and case studies infuses a proper dose of life and soul to his articles. He was proud that mainstream criminologists had paid attention to his work. But he was most proud of his students, current or past. He kept in touch with everyone – everyone! There was always time, with Carlo. He always took the time.

Carlo was, of course, an international criminology superstar. He was not the very first criminologist to use social network analysis, but he is the one who brought it to the masses. He made it understandable, relevant. Why do some people get ahead in crime? Because they manage their social networks better than others. Because they were mentored early in their career. It was about time we paid serious attention to this.

And now a lot of us are simply applying the Carlo principles in our own research. We are pursuing, in our own way, a little piece of the criminology of Carlo Morselli. With the help of Dr. Rémi Boivin and Dr. David Décary-Héту who are preparing a similarly themed special volume in *Global Crime*, we decided to do our part to honor his legacy by editing this volume of the *Canadian Journal of Criminology and Criminal Justice*. A single issue of either journal would not have been able to do justice to the richness and diversity of research projects that Carlo has spearheaded over the course of his career. This is why readers are encouraged to consider the two volumes as complementary, companion volumes¹. We also encourage readers interested in a review of Carlo's work to consult von Lampe's (2021) recent article *Remembering Carlo Morselli*.

¹ The *Global Crime* component special issue will be published in volume 23, issues 2&3 in Spring 2022: <https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/fglc20/current>

On the *CJCCJ* side, we selected manuscripts revolving around two major themes in Carlo's career: the development of criminal achievement as a conceptual and empirical framework (Nur and Nguyen; Tremblay, Morselli, and Charest), and the innovative use of social network data in new contexts of criminological interest (Carrington and Graham; Nolet, Mignon and Charette; Ryu and McCuish). On the *Global Crime* side, you will find other themes from Carlo's research, from patterns in organized crime or co-offending networks, to developments in using network data to think through disruption. The division of papers is of course not clear-cut, nor should it be if it is to capture the variety of influences found in any of Carlo's work.

Patterns in criminal achievement

In 2000, Dr. Pierre Tremblay and Carlo published their first of a series of papers on criminal achievement. Pierre and Carlo were struck by Wilson and Abrahamse's claims that offenders were prone to exaggerate or even lie about their criminal earnings (to rationalize their otherwise poor criminal output), to the point where none of these data could be trusted for empirical research. Tremblay and Morselli (2000) re-analyzed the same data, and instead found surprisingly reliable data on earnings. One of the main take-aways was not that most career criminals make large sums of money from crime, but there were enough examples of criminal success around to inspire a much larger segment of the less successful criminal populations. Success via criminal involvement was possible, attainable, and most had enough examples from their own career and those of their social networks to believe that it was within reach.

Two papers from this volume continue this line of inquiry. In *Anomie Reconsidered: Exaggerated Aspirations, Risk-taking and Criminal Achievement*, Tremblay, Morselli, and Charest get inside the logic of offender decision-making like few have done before by directly tackling the role of individual aspirations in criminal risk-taking. Their inquiry starts with an important yet rarely asked question to individuals involved in crime: how much legitimate money would it take for you to leave

your criminal career? Individuals who want more compensation to leave crime either earn large criminal earnings, have little confidence their ability to earn in conventional settings, or they are simply expressing their strong preference for a criminal lifestyle regardless of what they earn. What if we could actually measure the discrepancy between what offenders consider as adequate legitimate earnings compensation for desisting from crime entirely, and the actual legitimate earnings they reported? The larger the difference between what they want, and what they have, the more offenders are said to be in a state of anomie. And it is this state of anomie, of potential dissatisfaction between *the want* and *the have* that Tremblay et al. hypothesize as a driver of risk-taking preferences among criminals. Their results are clear: exaggerated aspirations are a strong, positive predictors of risk-taking in their sample. Their measurement of risk-taking is worth the read, in and of itself. Inspired by the pay-off matrix of jurors of consequences of making the right or wrong decision to convict or acquit accused offenders, the authors extract a measure of acceptable risks that offenders are willing to take by calculating the individual contributions of criminal hits made (the “right” decision to have committed a crime), the missed criminal opportunities (money they could have from crime), the failures of action (missed earnings from incarceration), and the potential legitimate earnings to be made if they desisted from crime entirely.

In *Getting By: Low Wages and Income Supplementation*, Nur and Nguyen continue the analysis of criminal earnings but focus on the relative balance that individuals achieve between the various sources of income (legal, informal, illegal). This question is often discussed within the framework of the rational choice perspective but rarely tackled head-on. Based on longitudinal data from a sample of adolescents who have begun the transition to adulthood, this study is interested in the decision to supplement legal income with income from informal or illegal activities and how human capital, conventional social capital, and criminal social capital are associated with these decisions. The results show that the sources of income of these adolescents are varied, and the probability of supplementing legal work with illicit income-generating activities is influenced by criminal social capital and low

legal wages. Differential mechanisms associated with decisions to supplement licit work inform the context that can lead to crimes and contribute to the planning of strategies promoting reintegration success.

Innovative uses of social network data in new contexts of criminological interest

Carlo was of course at the forefront of research on social networks and crime. Much of his research revolved around the idea that the structure of individual social networks had an impact on criminal careers. His very first articles, for instance, showed how the network structure of a drug trafficker helped him stay in business for 30 years (Morselli, 2001), and how it's the social network of a Mafiosi – not his reputation for violence – that allowed him to move through the ranks of an Italian crime family (Morselli, 2003). As his career progressed, Carlo explored the range of network effects on other aspects of criminal careers, from criminal earnings (Morselli & Tremblay, 2004) to detection avoidance inside criminal organizations (Morselli, 2010).

Two of the papers in this volume speak to this aspect of his research agenda. The first paper *Exploring the Reciprocal Relationship between Serious Victimization and Criminogenic Networks*, by Ryu and McCuish, aims to understand serious victimization and how it prospectively associates with future social network characteristics. Their analysis is based on longitudinal data of a sample of adjudicated young offenders. Findings show that the experiences of serious victimization were associated with a person's future network characteristics. This study is innovative in that it emphasizes the relationship between social environment and victimization at the individual-level. Previous studies have compartmentalized the explanation of victimizations within criminal careers by focusing primarily on criminal involvement or lifestyle characteristics.

The second paper, *The effect of the structure of prosocial and antisocial relationships on offenders' optimism toward desistance*, by Nolet, Charette, and Mignon, presents a mixed-method approach to understand how an incarcerated person's sociability features are intertwined with their

potential for re-entry, more specifically in their perception of their potential for desistance. The focus is on personal networks beyond the carceral setting, a dimension that is generally neglected in studies of re-entry. The authors distinguish between prosocial and antisocial ties, as well as between open and closed networks, showing that relative optimism towards desistance depends on specific combination of ties that favor individuals who have access to dense, prosocial connections.

Carlo was also interested in more meso, even macro level effects of networks. He was a leading figure in promoting the utility of social network analysis for examining how social structure shapes criminal activity (Morselli, 2009). Certain criminal opportunities emerge from fluid and adaptive structures that promotes cooperation between offenders (e.g. Ouellet, Boivin, Leclerc & Morselli, 2013; Morselli & Royer, 2008). The research note, *The interurban network of criminal collaboration in Canada*, by Carrington and Graham, is part of this tradition by focusing on the structure of criminal collaboration at the national level. The approach is innovative insofar as the unit of analysis resides in cities. The links that unite Canadian cities are based on offenders who engage in collaborative crime in more than one city, an innovative take on offender mobility that Carlo would have appreciated.

Conclusion

The broad spectrum of study objects represented in this issue bears witness to Carlo's remarkable versatility and the scope, implication, and applicability of his research work. The articles chosen in this special issue can only capture a small portion of the legacy left by Carlo. The criminology of Carlo Morselli was unique; the man himself was one of a kind. No small collection of papers can quite do justice to the intellectual loss we all suffered. But we hope it sparks new ideas for the current and next generation of criminologists to pursue the work he started.

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